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**Hausarbeit
The Italian migration to Argentina
during the late 19th and early 20th centuries**

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Introduction

Italian emigration, also referred to as the Italian diaspora, to Argentina during the late 19th and early 20th centuries constitutes a pivotal episode in the histories of both countries. This period is marked by a substantial and enduring movement of people, culture, and influence. This essay is guided by the research question of *why and how Italian migration to Argentina in the late 19th and early 20th centuries led to significant cultural integration of the Italian community into Argentine society.*

The aim of this essay is to examine the cultural dynamics and social integration processes of Italian immigrants in Argentina by analyzing the historical context of the migration and applying two esteemed sociological theories: Gordon’s Classical Theory of Assimilation and the Theory of Transnational Identities. It delves into the push and pull factors that drove Italian emigration to Argentina, settlement patterns, community structures, and sociological theories on assimilation and identity preservation within the Italian-Argentine experience. The primary objective is to explain the factors that facilitated the successful integration of Italian immigrants during this period. The significance of this essay lies in its contribution to the broader understanding of cultural integration within the context of mass migration.

Historical Overview of Italian Migration to Argentina

Argentina was the desired country for 15 percent of the 14 million Italians who emigrated between 1861 and 1915, representing 47 percent of all immigrants to Argentina. The influx of Italians to Argentina remained relatively consistent during this period, with a notable increase in migration occurring between 1901 and 1910 (República Argentina, 1925). Emigrants from

Northern Italy were more likely to travel alone, whereas those from the Southern regions often accompanied their families. Notably, most Italian emigrants originated from the southern regions, such as Campania, Calabria, and Sicily, as well as the northern regions, such as Veneto, Lombardy, and Piedmont (Ratti, 1931, pp. 446-454). Although many Italian immigrants initially intended to return to Italy once they had achieved financial stability, many made Argentina their permanent home (Frasca, 2014, pp. 109-132).

Economic opportunities, political and legal conditions, and social networks influenced the decision to emigrate from Italy to Argentina. Many Italians left because of challenging socio-economic conditions, including widespread poverty, high unemployment rates, and land scarcity due to fragmented ownership. Poor soil quality, outdated farming techniques, a devastating phylloxera epidemic in vineyards, and volcanic eruptions such as the 1906 eruption of Mount Vesuvius further strained agricultural livelihoods. Rapid population growth, especially in Southern Italy (Mezzogiorno), intensified competition for limited resources. Moreover, the political instability after the Italian unification (Risorgimento), characterized by regional tensions between the industrial north and the agrarian south, as well as widespread dissatisfaction with the government, further motivated emigration from Italy. Despite these formidable challenges, Italian immigrants showed remarkable resilience and determination in seeking a better life in Argentina (Baily, 1999, pp. 33-46).

Conversely, Argentina experienced a period of rapid economic growth known as the “Golden Age,” driven by the rapid expansion of railroads and telegraph lines and the overall modernization of the country. In addition, the export of land-intensive production products to expanding markets in Europe led to an expansion of Argentina’s international trade. Beginning in the 1860s, commercial agriculture was expanded, making it easier for immigrants to settle in Argentina (Lewis, 2001, pp. 51-62). The Italian diaspora played a critical role in this economic boom, creating a high demand for labor in Argentina, particularly in agriculture and infrastructure. The availability of land further supported this economic boom. In addition to these economic pull factors, the Argentine government provided various incentives to encourage immigration. Social and cultural factors also played an influential role, as established Italian communities and cultural affinities made Argentina an appealing place to live in (Baily, 1999, pp. 70-80).

Both the Argentine and Italian governments actively promoted migration between their respective countries, complementing the key push factors mentioned above.

On the one hand, the Argentine government played a pivotal role in attracting European immigrants, particularly from Italy. Juan B. Alberdi, a prominent figure in this endeavor and often

referred to as the father of the Argentine Constitution, played a crucial role in shaping the country's approach to immigration. He argued that Argentina's process relied heavily on the influx of educated, industrious, and well-mannered European immigrants. Emphasizing the need to form an intellectual class capable of leading the nation, Alberdi's concepts were subsequently incorporated into the Argentine Constitution of 1853 of the Argentine Confederation (Alberdi, 2002, pp. 95-101). Articles 20 and 25 specifically address the rights of immigrants and foreigners. Article 20 grants (citizenship) rights to foreigners, whereas Article 25 proclaims the federal government's responsibility to encourage European immigration (Rotondo, 2017, pp. 1-40). This historical perspective provides a deeper understanding of Argentina's policy of encouraging immigrants to populate the country and stimulate its economic growth.

On the other hand, in the fifty years preceding World War 1, successive Italian governments during this period actively facilitated emigration through nonrestrictive and even favorable legislation. The initial emigration law enacted in 1888 under the leadership of Prime Minister Francesco Crispi attempted to regulate Italy's growing emigration wave by requiring medical examinations, ensuring ship safety standards, and protecting emigrants' rights. Despite its progressive objectives, the law suffered from poor enforcement, bureaucratic obstacles, and insufficient consideration of regional differences (Soresina, 2016, pp. 723-746). Law No. 23 of 1901 further protected emigrants by abolishing the requirement for emigration agent authorizations, setting up regulated contracts between emigrants and navigation companies, and establishing the Commissariato Generale dell'Emigrazione (CGE) (De Luca, 1910; Del Giudice, 1989, pp. 749-773), which oversaw ticket prices, managed emigrants' legal obligations, and conducted inspections. Although it faced bureaucratic and jurisdictional disputes, as well as limited political backing and resources, its effectiveness was occasionally hampered (Soresina, 2016, pp. 723-746).

Furthermore, several prime ministers advocated for emigration to Argentina to alleviate economic hardships and to spread Italian culture (Manzotti, 1962). These policies were seen as part of "emigrant colonialism," as Choate terms the policies that specifically dealt with emigrant communities abroad. In 1887, Crispi viewed emigration as a tool for a nation-building force and the spread of *Italianità*, a term that encompasses the cultural, social, and political aspects of being Italian, and Crispi himself encouraged Italian-speaking people in the Americas to think of Italy as an 'ethnographic empire' (Choate, 2008, pp. 2, 29). The politician and economist Luigi Einaudi also argued that cultural exchange and trade resulting from open emigration were more sustainable in the long term than military or political domination (Einaudi, 1900, pp. 22-23).

The intertwined historical connections associated with Italian emigration to Argentina had a major influence on the socio-cultural and economic landscapes of both countries. Substantial Italian emigration to Argentina fostered lasting and profound relations between the two nations, which still serve as evidence of the lasting impact of these historical occurrences.

Cultural Integration: Factors and Processes

A combination of economic, social, and political factors facilitated the cultural integration of Italian immigrants in Argentina.

Italian immigrants contributed significantly to labor and industrial development. The 1935 industrial census revealed that foreigners accounted for 54 percent of all industrial owners in the country, 22 percent of whom were Italian. Notably, Italians also played a crucial role in the agricultural sector, bringing with them agricultural expertise. Adapting agricultural techniques from Italy to the distinct conditions of the Pampas was challenging but ultimately beneficial. In addition, immigrants also brought other professional skills and even introduced certain crops and production methods, demonstrating their innovative spirit and adaptability (Devoto, 2004, pp. 309-428).

Secondly, the influence of social factors was also significant. Argentina's social structure at that time differed from that of Europe, with a small elite, the *gente decente*, and a large group of non-elites, the *gente de pueblo* (Baily, 1999, pp. 69-73). The notion of a middle class was not widely recognized and articulated until the rise of Peronism in the 1940s. Although Germani identified a middle group that was estimated to comprise about one-third of the population in 1895 (Germani, 1955, pp. 218-219; Germani, 1966, pp. 165-182), it reflects a categorization based on specific socio-economic indicators rather than a fully articulated middle-class identity in a cultural or political sense. However, the influence of large immigrant groups, including Italians, contributed to the development of urban middle sectors that would later be identified as the middle class. This group was partly distinguished from the working class and the oligarchy by racial and cultural differentiation. The Italian influence was part of the larger narrative that "Argentines descend from the ships," meaning that Argentina's population was predominantly composed of European immigrants, which included a significant number of Italians who settled in urban areas and engaged in various trades, crafts, and professional occupations, helping to form a distinct middle-class identity (Garguin, 2007, pp. 161-184).

Furthermore, the dual settlement pattern of Italian immigrants both in urban centers such as Buenos Aires, La Plata, and Rosario, but also in rural areas of provinces like Córdoba and Santa Fe, where they were actively involved in agricultural activities, led to the formation of Italian

solid communities. In addition, the establishment of cultural institutions, such as theaters or choral groups, and Italian schools between 1860 and 1914, often overseen by Italian intellectuals, contributed to the promotion of education within the Italian community in Argentina while also reinforcing ethnic identity and advancing “civilization.” It is also noteworthy that Italian immigrants were instrumental in shaping a more open and socially mobile society in Argentina (Devoto, 2004, pp. 294-502).

Lastly, Italian immigrants played a notable role in Argentine politics from 1852 to 1912 despite limited direct participation and low electoral engagement due to elites’ fear that mass naturalization could upset the political balance of the process and immigrant disenchantment with limited electoral influence. Although the electoral reform law – the Sáenz Peña Law – in 1912 was effective, there were only a few immigrants in the Argentine parliament in 1916. Immigrants had to rely on Argentine citizens and political parties who were sympathetic to their causes to represent their interests. Significantly, the Socialist Party, the Radical Civic Union, and the Democratic Progressive Party found strong support in immigrant-dense areas, such as La Boca in Buenos Aires. In addition, Italian elites, particularly from the intellectual and political traditions of the Risorgimento, played a not to be underestimated role in Argentine politics, notably in founding institutions such as *Unione e Benevolenza* (Devoto, 2004, pp. 323-326). Despite the improvements in recent decades, Article 20 of the Argentinian Constitution, both today and back then, still excludes foreigners from participating in the political process.

Application of Gordon’s Classical Theory of Assimilation

Gordon’s classical theory of assimilation describes a multi-stage process in which an ethnic or immigrant group undergoes a series of assimilative steps, including cultural, structural, marital, identificational, attitude receptional, behavior receptional, and civic assimilation, ultimately leading to full integration into the host society. Notably, these stages are not strictly linear or uniform, and different groups may experience them to varying degrees.

Cultural or behavioral assimilation or acculturation involves the adoption by individuals or groups of cultural patterns of the host society, such as language, customs, and values (Gordon, 1964, pp. 70-76). A clear example is reciprocal cultural influence (Gordon, 1964, pp. 138-139), as seen with Italian immigrants who adopted but also influenced Argentine Spanish, which is still evident today in various aspects of the language, including vocabulary, pronunciation and intonation (riolatense Spanish), syntax, and slang language (Lunfardo). They also brought certain gestures and expressions typical of Italian culture into everyday Argentine interactions, such as the use of hand gestures to complement speech (Lipski, 2014, pp. 53-56).

Structural assimilation involves the large-scale entry of immigrants into the social cliques, clubs, and institutions of the host society, particularly at the primary group level, such as families, friendships, and intimate social networks. This phase is crucial because it often precedes other forms of assimilation, such as marital and civic assimilation (Gordon, 1964, pp. 70-76). Initially, Italian immigrants established their own schools to maintain their language and culture. However, as Argentine public schools became more accessible in the early 20th century, more Italian children attended these schools than Italian ones, promoting further linguistic integration (Devoto, 2004, pp. 242, 279).

Marital assimilation, also known as amalgamation, refers to the intermarriage between immigrants and indigenous population, resulting in cultural blending and the gradual disappearance of ethnic distinctions (Gordon, 1964, pp. 70-76). Despite the Argentine government's encouragement of inter-ethnic marriages as a benefit to the country's economy, there were high rates of endogamy and hidden endogamy to maintain the persistence of Italian cultural and family ties (Baily, 1999, pp. 152-156). Nevertheless, as the gender imbalance among Italians grew from the 1870s onward, intermarriages between immigrants and Creoles increased (Szuchman, 1977, pp. 24-50).

Identification assimilation occurs when immigrants begin to identify primarily with the host society rather than with their own ethnic group, marking their integration into the national identity (Gordon, 1964, pp. 70-76). Italian immigrants and their descendants gradually developed a dual identity – Italian-Argentine – that combined pride in their Italian heritage with a solid Argentine national identity (Devoto, 2006, pp. 78-81).

Attitude receptional assimilation refers to the absence of prejudice within the host society towards the immigrant group, indicating acceptance and equality in social attitudes (Gordon, 1964, pp. 70-76). By the mid-20th century, Italians had become widely accepted in Argentine society, largely due to their significant contributions to the economy and embodiment of values like hard work and strong family ties (Baily, 1999, pp. 218-222).

Behavior receptional assimilation is characterized by the absence of discriminatory behavior against the immigrant group, allowing them to participate fully in all aspects of society, both public and private, signifying complete behavioral assimilation (Gordon, 1964, pp. 70-76). Italians generally experienced minimal discrimination, benefiting from positive societal and governmental attitudes (Baily, 1999, p. 220). Their socio-economic status improved over time, mainly due to education and integration, further diminishing biases and discrimination (Devoto, 2004, pp. 422-423).

The final stage is civic assimilation, which happens when immigrants and the host society share common civic values and political institutions without major conflicts (Gordon, 1964, pp. 70-76). Eventually, Italian immigrants, especially their descendants, participated in local and national politics and adopted common civic values.

Theory of Transnational Identities

The term “transnationalism” is used to describe the ways in which immigrants establish and maintain multi-layered social networks that bridge their societies of origin and settlement. These processes give rise to transnational social fields that transcend geographic, cultural, and political boundaries (Basch et al., 1993, pp. 5-10).

Italian immigrants in Argentina maintained strong ties to their homeland through communication, remittances, and even periodic returns to Italy or sending their children there. As mentioned earlier, the dual identity has blended Italian and Argentine customs, which is, for instance, in the fusion of Italian cuisine with Argentine food traditions, creating dishes such as “*milanesa*” and “*fainá*”. Italian culture and language have also been promoted through cultural diplomacy initiatives, including the establishment of the Dante Alighieri Society and the support of the Italian government. In addition, Argentina was among the first countries to have diplomatic relations with Italy (Esteri, 1886, p. 56). Today, Italian schools continue to preserve cultural identity and facilitate bilingualism among the descendants of Italian immigrants.

Relevance of Gordon’s classical theory of assimilation and the Transnational Identity framework in the context of the Italian Diaspora to Argentina

Classical assimilation theory posits that immigrants eventually abandon their original cultural identities and fully assimilate into the host society. In contrast, transnationalism recognizes and emphasizes the ongoing connections that immigrants maintain across borders, allowing multiple identities and loyalties to co-exist simultaneously. Both theories explain the integration of Italian immigrants into Argentine society. While Gordon’s theory focuses mainly on the step-by-step process through which Italian immigrants integrated into Argentine society, the transnational identity theory offers a more nuanced understanding of the Italian migration experience, particularly in terms of maintaining ties with Italy while integrating into Argentine society.

Nevertheless, both theories have several limitations when applied to the Italian migration to Argentina. On the one hand, Gordon's theory implies a linear progression through assimilated stages, which underestimates the complex and varied integration process. For that matter,

cultural assimilation did not necessarily precede structural assimilation, both occurred concurrently and influenced each other. Moreover, it assumes a one-way process in which the immigrant group assimilates into the host society without fully considering the transformation of the host society by the immigrants. It also does not fully take into account the reciprocal influence of immigrants. Finally, it focuses heavily on assimilation as the end goal, potentially overlooking transnational ties that were critical among Italian-Argentines.

On the other hand, while acknowledging these ties, the transnational identity framework may overemphasize the persistence of Italian identity and underestimate the extent of genuine assimilation into Argentine society, including structural integration.

Conclusion

Italian immigrants played a crucial and positive role in Argentina's economy, particularly in agriculture and industry. Their expertise was an eminent factor during Argentina's Golden Age of economic growth, leading to increased social mobility and integration of the middle class. By forming solid communities with various institutions, Italian immigrants reinforced ethnic identity while facilitating integration. The integration process involved the adoption of Argentine cultural norms and the retention of Italian cultural ties. Their dual identity allowed them to integrate while maintaining a connection to their homeland and mutual cultural assimilation, especially in language and social customs. Gordon's classical theory of assimilation and the transnational identity framework offer valuable perspectives on Italian migration to Argentina. Gordon's theory helps explain the stages of integration, while the transnational identity framework highlights immigrants' ongoing connections to Italy and dual identities. Nevertheless, neither framework fully captures the complexity of the Italian immigrant experience in Argentina, suggesting that the combination of both may provide a more comprehensive understanding.

The specific case of Italians' migration to Argentina illustrates how economic opportunities, political conditions, and social networks drive large-scale migration. It provides a precedent for how host countries can integrate large immigrant populations and how these populations can contribute to their new societies.

Works Cited

- República Argentina, D. d. (1925). *Resumen estadístico del movimiento migratorio en la República Argentina, 1857-1924*. Buenos Aires: Talleres Gráficos del Ministerio de Agricultura de la Nación.
- Baily, S. L. (1999). *Immigrants in the Lands of Promise: Italians in Buenos Aires and New York City, 1870 - 1914*. Cornell University Press.

- Lewis, D. K. (2001). *The History of Argentina*. USA: Westport [etc.] : Greenwood Press.
- Manzotti, F. (1962). *La polemica sull'emigrazione nell'Italia unita (fino alla prima guerra mondiale)*. (D. Alighieri, Ed.) Città di Castello.
- Devoto, F. J. (2004). *Historia de la Inmigración en la Argentina* (Vol. 2 ed.). Buenos Aires: Sudamericana.
- Gordon, M. M. (1964). *Assimilation in American life: the role of race, religion, and national origins*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Szuchman, M. D. (1977). The Limits of the Melting Pot in Urban Argentina: Marriage and Integration in Córdoba, 1868-1909. *The Hispanic American Historical Review*, 57(1), 24-50.
- Ratti, A. M. (1931). Italian Migration Movements, 1876 to 1926. In W. F. Willcox, *International Migrations, Volume 2: Interpretations* (Vol. 2, pp. 454, 446). NBER.
- Alberdi, J. B. (2002). Immigration as a Means of Progress. In G. Montaldo, & G. Neuzeilles, *The Argentina Reader: History, Culture, Politics* (pp. 95-101). Durham, NC: Duke University Press.
- Rotondo, F. (2017, 12). Italiani d'Argentina. Dall'accoglienza alla 'difesa sociale' (1853-1910). *Historia e ius. Rivista di storia giuridica dell'età medievale e moderna*(13), 1-40.
- Soresina, M. (2016). Italian emigration policy during the Great Migration Age, 1888–1919: the interaction of emigration and foreign policy. *Journal of Modern Italian Studies*, 723-746.
- Del Giudice, F. (1989). Il Commissariato generale dell'emigrazione nel suo sviluppo storico, 1901-1928. *La formazione della diplomazia italiana 1861–1915*, 749–773.
- Germani, G. (1966, November). Mass Immigration and Modernization in Argentina. *Studies in Comparative International Development*, 2, 165-182.
- Basch, L., Glick-Schiller, N., & Szanton-Blanc, C. (1993). *Nations Unbound: Transnational Projects, Postcolonial Predicaments, and Deterritorialized Nation-States*. Routledge.
- Esteri, M. p. (1886). *Annuario diplomatico del Regno d'Italia*. Rome: Ministero per gli Affari Esteri.
- Garguin, E. (2007, August 13). 'Los Argentinos Descendemos de los Barcos': The Racial Articulation of Middle Class Identity in Argentina (1920–1960). *Latin American and Caribbean Ethnic Studies*, 2(2), pp. 161-184.
- Frasca, S. (2014). Birds of Passage: The Immigrants Return Home. In S. Frasca, *Italian Birds of Passage* (pp. 109-132). New York, USA: Palgrave Macmillan.
- De Luca, P. E. (1910). Sull'ordinamento dei servizi di emigrazione. *Della emigrazione europea ed in particolare di quella italiana*, 3.
- Einaudi, L. (1900). *Un principe mercante. Studio sulla espansione coloniale italiana*. Turin.
- Choate, M. A. (2008). *Emigration Nation: The Making of Italy Abroad*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Germani, G. (1955). *Estructura social de la Argentina: análisis estadístico*.
- Lipski, J. M. (2014). The many facets of Spanish dialect diversification in Latin America. In S. S. Mufwene, *Iberian Imperialism and Language Evolution in Latin America*. Chicago, United States of America: University of Chicago Press.
- Devoto, F. J. (2006). *Historia de los Italianos en la Argentina*. Buenos Aires: Editorial Biblos.

Declaration of Originality

I hereby declare that I have written this seminar paper on my own, have not used any sources or aids other than those specified, and have marked the passages taken from them as such. All

aids used are listed in the table below. Regarding the use of Large Language Models (LLM, e.g. Chat-GPT), I have archived the entire LLM interaction history with reference to the submitted work and can present it upon request. This seminar paper has not been presented in this or a similar form in any other course.

Name of Aid/ Tool	Purpose
DeepL Translate	Translation
Grammarly	Grammar and spelling check
Scholar GPT	Research assistant
Consensus	Research assistant

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